

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL FORMATION OF FUTURE FINANCIAL STUDENTS

М.С.Бердибаев,

Ажиниёз номидаги Нукус давлат педагогика институти
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8372334>

Резюме: Мақолада интерфаол таълим технологияларининг талабаларнинг ижодий фикрлашини ривожлантиришдаги аҳамияти ҳақида айтилган. Таълим технологиялари асосида ижодий фикрлашнинг психо-педагогик масалаларининг ечими белгиланган.

Калит сўзлар: интерфаол технологиялар, таълим жараёни, билим, шаклланиш, ижодий фаолият.

Резюме: В статье освещена роль интерактивных образовательных технологий в развитии творческого мышления студентов. Обозначены психолого-педагогические задачи, решаемые в процессе развития творческого мышления на основе образовательных технологий

Ключевые слова: интерактивные технологии, образовательный процесс, знание, формирование, творческая деятельность.

Summary: In article the of interactive educational technologies in developing of creative activity of students are considered. Pedagogical and psychological tasks, which should be solved in the process of creative thinking based on educational technology are denoted.

Key words: interactive technologies, educational process, knowledge, formation, creative activity.

It is known that today, with the rapid development of science and technology, the volume of scientific knowledge, understanding and imagination is increasing dramatically. On the one hand, this ensures its differentiation through the development of new areas and departments of science and technology, and on the other hand, it creates a process of integration between sciences. Therefore, in such conditions, the demands placed on highly qualified teachers who are able to educate the mature generation in the spirit of universal and national values that have been formed over centuries and who have mastered the fundamentals of pedagogy are increasing. sciences, pedagogical and psychological methods, have a high level of professional training and use modern pedagogical and information technologies, it is necessary to prepare creative teachers with applied skills and abilities.

The following scientific research is being conducted aimed at developing the competencies of future financiers based on a person-oriented approach:

- content of training and its educational and methodological support;
- educational technologies;
- ensuring the objectivity of knowledge control;
- development of technologies for the development of competent financiers based on a person-oriented approach, taking into account the requirements of world standards;
- conducting scientific research on the organization of independent learning in lessons and in extracurricular activities is acquiring scientific and practical significance.

For future financiers, higher education is the most suitable period for self-improvement and development of qualities, knowledge, abilities and skills that are important from a professional point of view for the successful implementation of teaching activities. In this process, future financiers embody such situations as collecting, storing, transferring their knowledge, creating their logical structure and learning to use it effectively when organizing their professional activities in the future. Today, future financiers are methodically taught: - the need for forms of active education and social need are not fully satisfied- that they do not have sufficient professional and pedagogical training to organize educational activities aimed at professional development;

- lack of necessary conditions for independent choice of content, method and modern teaching tools in the process of professional development;

- it is necessary to determine ways and methods of eliminating imbalances, such as insufficient development of the necessary knowledge and skills, to draw the necessary scientific conclusions and develop scientific, practical and methodological recommendations by conducting scientific research and experimental tests on their basis [1.160]. Today, a training concept is being promoted that places future financiers at the center of the learning process, transforming them from mere listeners into active subjects. To achieve this goal, the content of educational programs and teaching technologies are regularly updated. It is also necessary to consider the possibility of creating interactive tasks during the study of each educational topic, department, because financiers require the use of special technologies to ensure interactivity in the process of mastering different educational subjects. Initially, these technologies were reflected in textbooks and manuals published in Uzbekistan. N.N. Azizkho'jaeva "Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skill", Sh. Shodmonova, N.S. Mirsagatova, G.N. Ibragimova, M.T. Mirsolievalar "Pedagogical technologies" methodological guide, U.I. Inoyatov, N.A. Muslimov, D.I. Rozieva, M.H.Usmonbaeva base the following types of interactive technologies: problem-based education, developmental education, differentiated education, cooperative education, modular education, game technologies, distance education, independent education. The implementation of interactive technologies in the educational process provides the basis for the professional development of future financiers, allowing the implementation of a group form of training, team work, and cooperation. In such circumstances, future financiers have a great responsibility to master the training course. Interactive technologies not only form activity, creativity and independence of future financiers in the process of assimilation of information, but also contribute to the full realization of educational goals.

From this point of view, each form of interactive work with prospective financiers allows for the use of specific technologies. Including:

1. Working together in pairs: "Work sitting face to face", "Work in pairs and together".
2. Work in small groups: "Aquarium" method.
3. Interactive games: "Role-playing games".
4. Discussion-based teaching technology: such as the "I choose my point of view" method [2.104].

Teachers are using a number of interactive methods in the course of the lesson. So far we have come across several types of teaching technologies. There are types of these technologies such as "Brainstorming", "Boomerang", "Fish Skeleton", "BBB" technology, "Insert table", "Lily flower", "Can you think", "Cluster". Of course, organizing lessons using

such technologies will make it interesting and effective. Based on the above-mentioned ideas, it is possible to develop the creativity of future financiers by using interactive teaching methods and technologies in the process of higher education. In this, professors and teachers should take into account the specific characteristics and capabilities of the group of future financiers, because with the help of these methods and technologies, theoretical knowledge and practical experience are acquired simultaneously. This, in turn, serves to develop the future financiers' professional point of view, worldview, speech, and logical thinking. In addition, they develop critical thinking about pedagogical knowledge and events. As a result, they will have the opportunity to realize and realize their individual creative abilities. Therefore, it is necessary to organize interactive learning situations in such a way that future financiers should clearly imagine the connection between new and acquired knowledge. As a result, they find alternative solutions to a particular problem, make discoveries. In the process of working together, they form their own ideas using different tools [2.125].

It is necessary for the teacher to be able to see each lesson as a whole and to plan the future lesson process. It is very important for the teacher to create a technological map of the future lesson, because the technological map of the lesson is created based on each subject, the subject taught for each lesson, the nature of the subject, the possibilities and needs of future funders. As a result of the analysis of many scientific sources, we were able to determine the specific features of interactive teaching that is carried out in the process of professional and pedagogical education. Interactive teaching methods and technologies are directed to meet the educational needs of future financiers. Including:

1. The content of the interactive training process should be related to the needs of future financiers to acquire professional knowledge. It is necessary to take into account the personal strengths, perspectives, and knowledge levels of future financiers.

2. In the process of interactive training, future financiers will gain additional confidence in their abilities, learn universal values, and have a sense of responsibility for their educational activities.

3. With the help of trainings, business games, future financiers will be able to determine their positions regularly, because the form of teamwork requires regular determination of one's position, resolute defense of one's point of view. As a result, common solutions are adopted in agreement with group members, and future financiers develop skills to work as a whole team and demonstrate their abilities in this process.

4. In the process of interactive training, future financiers themselves independently demonstrate their creative abilities, actively acquire professional qualities.

5. Future financiers consistently acquire the skills to apply the acquired knowledge and professional qualities in their future activities.

6. The benevolent atmosphere, mutual trust and cooperation created in the process of interactive training will create a favorable opportunity for the creative growth of future financiers and will be the basis for regular development of their creative abilities [2.152].

It is known that in higher education, there are many difficulties in teaching future financiers in higher mathematics, mathematics, teaching students, and most of them arise due to the insufficient improvement of methodological training of future financiers. This in itself shows the need to further strengthen the attention to the methodical preparation of students in the teaching of labor education in all higher education institutions of our Republic. It shows

that the development of ways, means and methods of provision at the level of requirements of state educational standards is one of the urgent issues [3.80].

Thus, the design of interactive technologies requires the sequential and consistent implementation of practical didactic activities. Interactive teaching technologies are considered to be a technology that can form the knowledge, skills and competencies that guarantee the fulfillment of functional obligations in accordance with the task and the personal qualities considered important for the future professional activity.

Адабиётлар:

1. Йўлдошев Ж.Ф., Усмонов С.А. Педагогик технология асослари. – Тошкент: РТМ, 2004. – Б. 104.
2. Монахов В.М. Технологические основы проектирования и конструирования учебного процесса. – Волгоград: Перемена, 1995.
3. Муслимов Н.А, Уразова М.Б., Эшпулатов Ш.Н. Касб таълими ўқитувчиларининг касбий компетентлигини шакллантириш технологияси. – Тошкент: Fan va texnologiya, 2013. – Б. 160.
4. Berdibaev M. THE INDEPENDENT WORK OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF MATHEMATICS AS A METHOD OF FORMING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 4.
5. Berdibaev, Maman. "THE INDEPENDENT WORK OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF MATHEMATICS AS A METHOD OF FORMING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY." European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol 7.4 (2019).
6. Berdibaev, M. (2019). THE INDEPENDENT WORK OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF MATHEMATICS AS A METHOD OF FORMING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 7(4).

